

Mass transfer at vapor-liquid interfaces of H₂O + CO₂ mixtures studied by molecular dynamics simulation

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In many industrial applications as well as in nature, the mass transfer of CO₂ at vapor-liquid interfaces in aqueous systems plays an important role. In this work, this process was studied on the atomistic level using non-equilibrium molecular dynamics simulations. In a first step, a molecular model of the system CO₂ + water was developed that represents both bulk and interfacial equilibrium properties well. This system is characterized by a very large adsorption and enrichment of CO₂ at the vapor-liquid interface. Then, non-equilibrium mass transfer simulations were carried out using a method that was developed recently: CO₂ is inserted into a the vapor phase of a simulation box which contains a liquid slab. Surprising effects are observed at the interface such as a net repulsion of CO₂ particles from the interface and a complex time dependence of the amount of CO₂ adsorbed at the interface.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Properties of mixtures of water + CO₂ are critical for many applications such as food technology, climatology, enhanced oil recovery, and fluid separation processes. In many of these cases, the mass transfer of CO₂ at vapor-liquid interfaces plays an important role. Due to the significant practical importance, thermophysical properties of the system water + CO₂ have been comprehensively studied in the past, e.g. regarding the gas solubility¹⁻³, transport properties⁴⁻⁶, and interfacial properties⁷⁻¹¹. Thermophysical properties of the system water + CO₂ have been extensively examined using both experiments¹⁻³ and theoretical models^{4,8,12-14}.

The system water + CO₂ exhibits a highly non-ideal phase behavior, namely a type III phase behavior according to the *van Koynenburg and Scott* classification¹⁵. Type III phase behavior is characterized by two critical lines and a vapor-liquid-liquid (VLL) equilibrium three-phase line. For type III mixtures, the two components usually have strongly differing critical temperatures as well as particularly weak cross-interactions. This is also the case for the system water + CO₂, where the interactions among water molecules are dominated by hydrogen bonding, whereas CO₂ molecules have significant dispersive and quadrupolar interactions¹⁶. This results in a low mutual solubility of the two components. Moreover, the system water + CO₂ has several peculiarities such as a barotropic inversion⁹, a solubility minimum of water in CO₂¹⁷, and an intriguing behavior of the surface tension with respect to the VLL three-phase equilibrium and wetting⁸.

Interfacial properties of the system water + CO₂ have received significant attention in the past – especially the surface tension^{18,19} and the wetting properties^{8,20}. This is not only due to the fact that water itself has a particularly high surface tension, but also due to the fact that the non-ideal phase behavior has important consequences for the interfacial properties, e.g. the presence of a three-phase VLL equilibrium for the surface tension⁸. A significant amount of experimental studies have been carried out focusing on the surface tension, e.g. Refs.^{7,8,18,21}. At times, also the adsorption of CO₂ at the interface was studied based on experimental data¹². Experimental data on the atomistic structure of the interface of the system water + CO₂ is presently not available.

Macroscopically, fluid interfaces are treated as two-dimensional objects, while in reality, their thickness spans over a few nanometers. Within the interface, interesting changes in

the system’s thermodynamic and structural behavior are often observed – especially for mixtures^{22,23}. For elucidating the nanoscopic structure of fluid interfaces, both molecular simulation computer experiments, i.e. molecular dynamics (MD) or Monte Carlo (MC) simulations^{24,25}, as well as different theories can be used^{26–28}. Both computational routes have been applied for studying the atomistic equilibrium structure of the system water + CO₂^{8,9,12,13,29–31}. From these computational studies, it is known that CO₂ strongly accumulates at the vapor-liquid interface. While the total density changes monotonously across the vapor-liquid interface, this does not hold for the density of the individual components. At fluid interfaces of the system water + CO₂, non-monotonic density profiles of CO₂ are usually observed. This phenomenon, which is referred to as *enrichment*^{23,32,33}, has also been observed for several other systems, where the density of the low-boiling component has a distinct maximum at the interface. The enrichment strongly depends on the mixture type^{34–36} and the thermodynamic condition³⁷. High enrichment of a low-boiling component is usually observed for strongly non-ideal mixtures with unlike interactions^{33,34,36}, low temperatures^{33,37}, and low mole fraction of the low-boiling component^{33,37,38}. For the system water + CO₂, a particularly high enrichment of CO₂ at the interface has been reported^{12,13,29,33}.

For many processes involving the system water + CO₂, not only static, but also dynamic interfacial properties are important. Mass transfer across fluid interfaces has received significant attention in recent years since there are reasons to believe that nanoscopic interfacial properties might affect the mass transfer – especially the monotonicity behavior of the density profiles. According to Fickian theory, the enrichment would be an obstacle to mass transfer. The enrichment is therefore believed to have an influence on the interfacial mass transfer^{23,24,39–43}. The system water + CO₂ is an excellent candidate for studying the influence of the enrichment on mass transfer due to the particularly large enrichment of CO₂ at the interface. Most computational studies on interfaces of the system water + CO₂ focus on (static) equilibrium properties, e.g. Refs.^{7,18,21}. *Matsumoto*⁴⁴ studied equilibrium dynamic properties, i.e. self-diffusion of CO₂ at a water interface. Dynamic non-equilibrium properties and processes on the atomistic level at vapor-liquid interfaces of the system water + CO₂ have, to the best of our knowledge, not yet been investigated.

For studying dynamic interfacial properties and processes on the atomistic scale, non-equilibrium molecular dynamics (NEMD) simulations can be used. Mass transfer at fluid interfaces has been frequently studied in the literature using NEMD simulations – yet, mostly

for simple systems, e.g. Refs.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷. NEMD simulation studies are available on transport parallel^{48,49} and normal to a fluid interface^{46,50}; the sole focus of this work is on mass transfer normal to the interface. Most studies on mass transfer normal to the interface consider evaporation or condensation in pure components^{45,51-55}. Mass transfer in mixtures has not been studied as systematically using NEMD simulations. Nevertheless, different simulation scenarios have been proposed and tested for studying mass transfer at vapor-liquid interfaces in mixtures^{50,56-59}, which comprises both stationary^{50,59} and non-stationary methods^{57,58}. NEMD mass transfer simulations in mixtures with fluid interfaces are challenging for multiple reasons: The insertion and/ or removal of particles; the interface exhibits fluctuations regarding its position; sampling observables with sufficient resolution at non-equilibrium conditions; and various relevant effects and properties are superimposed, e.g. the bulk phase solubility, bulk phase transport coefficients, and different interfacial properties. In Ref.⁵⁰, we proposed a stationary NEMD simulation method. Yet, especially the fluctuating interface position poses challenges in this method. In Ref.⁵⁷, we developed a non-stationary NEMD method using replicas to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio. This method was also applied in Ref.⁶⁰ for systematically studying different model mixtures. Based on that experience, the non-stationary method⁵⁷ proved significantly more robust and providing more detailed insights compared to the stationary method⁵⁰. As in our previous works^{50,57,60}, in practically all interfacial mass transfer studies on mixtures, simple fluids, i.e. Lennard-Jones mixtures were considered^{50,56-62}. Hence, NEMD mass transfer studies on real substance systems are very scarce.

In this work, we used the non-stationary NEMD simulation method from Ref.⁵⁷ to study the mass transfer of CO₂ at vapor-liquid interfaces in the system water + CO₂. In a first step, the mixture model was adjusted to gas solubility data and validated for phase equilibrium properties in a wide temperature and composition range. Using that calibrated mixture model, both equilibrium and non-equilibrium interfacial properties were predicted. Thereby, the behavior of CO₂ at the vapor-liquid interface of water + CO₂ mixtures is elucidated at both equilibrium and non-equilibrium conditions.

This work is outlined as follows: First, the employed molecular models and simulation methods are presented. Then, the results are presented and discussed, starting with the equilibrium properties and, subsequently, the non-equilibrium properties. Finally, conclusions are drawn.

II. METHODS AND MODELS

A. Force field models

A large number of force fields are available in the literature for both CO₂ and H₂O^{63–65}. For both substances, different types of force fields have been developed, e.g. all-atom, united-atom, and coarse grain^{66–68} as well as rigid, flexible, and reactive force fields^{65,66,69,70}. Since an important focus of this work is on the structure of the vapor-liquid interface, we chose all-atom force fields for both substances. We do not consider chemical reactions and assume CO₂ behaving as an inert gas in water. Flexible force fields regarding the intramolecular interactions can provide a more detailed description regarding the structure and some dynamic properties^{70–72}, yet they come with significantly higher computational costs and complexity⁷³. Therefore, we chose rigid force fields in this work. Rigid all-atom force fields have been systematically compared in the literature regarding their performance for describing different properties for both CO₂^{74–77} and H₂O^{65,66,78}. In this work, we focus on vapor-liquid equilibrium properties. For CO₂, we used the model proposed by *Merker et al.*⁷⁵. For H₂O, we used the TIP4P/2005 water model proposed by *Abascal & Vega*⁷⁹. The CO₂ model of *Merker et al.*⁷⁵ provides an excellent description of bulk VLE properties, i.e. it describes experimental data for the saturated liquid density with an accuracy of 0.4%, 1.8% for the vapor pressure, and 8.1% for the enthalpy of vaporization⁷⁵, which is due to the fact that VLE properties were the focus in the model development. The TIP4P/2005 water model, yields an excellent description of the saturated liquid density (below 1% up to 450 K)^{79,80}, but significant deviations for the vapor pressure^{65,80}. This is due to the fact that the parametrization was carried out considering a wider basis of properties^{65,79}. The TIP4P/2005 water model consists of one Lennard-Jones interaction site and three point charges⁷⁹. The *Merker et al.*⁷⁵ CO₂ model consists of three Lennard-Jones interaction sites and a point quadrupole.

Many molecular models of real substances that were parameterized to yield good descriptions of bulk properties, yield results for the surface tension that are higher than the experimental values. This has been demonstrated for many force fields^{81,82}. The CO₂ model from *Merker et al.*⁷⁵ overestimates the surface tension by about 20%⁸³. The TIP4P/2005 force field describes the surface tension of water well⁸⁴, with mean deviations of below 5%.

For describing the mixed interactions, combination rules need to be applied. In this work, the dispersive-repulsive cross-interactions in the system were modeled using the modified Lorentz-Berthelot^{85,86} combination rules

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_{ii} + \sigma_{jj}}{2}, \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \xi \sqrt{\varepsilon_{ii} \varepsilon_{jj}}, \quad (2)$$

where ξ indicates the binary interaction parameter in the mixture of components i and j . The binary cross-interaction parameter ξ was fitted to experimental data of the Henry's law coefficient (see below). The parameter ξ is a state-independent constant. The modeling of the polar interactions is based on the classical laws of electrostatics and does not require an additional cross-interaction parameter.

Interfacial properties were studied in this work at three temperatures, namely $T = 291.65$ K, 372.08 K, 452.97 K, which corresponds to about $0.45 T_{c,\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $0.57 T_{c,\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, and $0.7 T_{c,\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, respectively, with $T_{c,\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 647.1$ K being the critical point temperature of water.

For the evaluation of the bulk phase equilibrium properties, the PCP-SAFT equation of state (EOS)⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹ was used; more specifically the water + carbon dioxide mixture model proposed by *Niño-Amézquita et al.*¹³. In Ref.¹³, the performance of their model was systematically validated with experimental phase equilibrium data and good agreement was obtained.

B. Equilibrium MD simulations

Henry's law constant simulations

The cross-interaction parameter ξ describing the unlike dispersive interactions in the mixture (cf. Eq. (2)) was fitted to experimental gas solubility data, i.e. Henry's law constant $H_{\text{CO}_2,\text{w}}$ of CO_2 in water. The experimental data was taken from the Dortmund data base⁹⁰. The Henry's law constant describes the gas solubility at infinite dilution and is, therefore, an excellent measure for characterizing the interaction between a solute particle solely with solvent particles and for parametrizing ξ . In this section, first, the parametrization approach is described, then, the simulation protocol for sampling the Henry's law constant is given.

Five simulations at different ξ values were carried out for determining the corresponding Henry's law constant. This was done for three temperatures ($T = 290, 335, 380$ K). For each

of these three temperatures, a reference value was determined from an interpolation of the closest experimental data for $H_{\text{CO}_2,\text{w}}$. For a given temperature, the Henry’s law constant results for the different ξ values were compared to the reference values. The optimal ξ value for a given temperature was then determined by linear interpolation between the sampling points that were closest to the experimental $H_{\text{CO}_2,\text{w}}$ data. The final value $\xi = 1.062$ was determined as the arithmetic mean of the ξ values from the three temperatures. For the evaluation of the fit, Henry’s law constants were determined in a wider temperature range using the determined ξ value. The results were compared with all available Henry’s law constant data (see discussion below).

The MD simulations for determining Henry’s law constant were carried out using the simulation engine *ms2*^{91,92}. Thereby, homogeneous liquid states of pure water were simulated. In these pure component states, test particles of CO_2 were inserted for computing its solubility at infinite dilution in water⁹³. The simulations were carried out in the NpT ensemble with 1024 solvent particles. In the simulations, the residual chemical potential at infinite dilution $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^\infty$ of CO_2 was sampled using *Widom’s* test particle method⁹⁴. Henry’s law constants of CO_2 in water were then computed as

$$H_{\text{CO}_2,\text{w}} = \rho'_w T \exp(\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^\infty/T), \tag{3}$$

where ρ'_w is the saturated liquid density of water and T is the temperature. The equilibration of the pure component solvent was carried out for 250,000 time steps and the production was carried out for 1,500,000 time steps. The time step was $\delta\tau = 1.2$ fs. The statistical uncertainty of the Henry’s law constant results was estimated to be three times the standard deviation of 50 block averages with the size of 10,000 time steps. The pressure of the NpT simulation was chosen to be 5% above the pure component water vapor pressure. The cut-off radius was 17.5 Å.

Direct VLE simulations

For determining vapor-liquid interfacial properties, MD simulations were carried out, where a vapor and a liquid phase ‘directly’ coexist that are separated by an interface. The simulations were carried out with the simulation engine *ls1 mardyn*⁹⁵. A liquid phase was placed as a slab in the middle of a square slab-shaped simulation volume, so that it is in contact with a vapor phase on each side. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in all directions. This simulation setup was used in this work for determining equilibrium properties

as well as for determining non-equilibrium properties under mass transfer conditions. The equilibrium simulations are described here; the non-equilibrium simulations are described in the following section.

Direct VLE simulations were carried out at three temperatures, namely $T = 291.65$ K, 372.08 K, and 452.97 K. For each temperature, at least seven state points were considered. The state points are characterized in the following by their liquid phase mole fraction x'_{CO_2} and the temperature T .

The equilibrium simulations were performed in the NVT ensemble with at least $N = 16,000$ particles (details are given in the Supplementary Material - Section I). The equations of motion were solved using a leapfrog integrator⁹⁶. The time step was $\delta\tau = 2$ fs. The initial densities and compositions employed in the simulations were taken from the PCP-SAFT EOS model to ensure fast equilibration.

The elongation of the simulation box normal to the interface (here the z -coordinate) was 26 nm and the thickness of the liquid slab was in the range $4.2 \dots 6.2$ nm. The elongation in the directions parallel to the interfaces was at least 9 nm. Thermodynamic properties are sensitive to the truncation of the intermolecular potential and the applied long-range correction scheme⁹⁷⁻¹⁰². For all simulations carried out in this work, the cut-off radius was set to 17.5 \AA using a center-of-mass cut-off scheme. A slab-based long-range correction scheme was employed to incorporate the long-range Lennard-Jones interactions and account for the inhomogeneity of the system^{98,100}.

The system was equilibrated for at least 2 ns, followed by a production phase of at least 4 ns. Density and pressure profiles were computed in block averages of $100,000$ time steps during the production phase. The profiles were determined using $N = 600$ bins, each with a width of $\Delta z = 0.0433$ nm. The origin of the z -axis of the interfacial profiles was chosen where $\rho_{\text{tot}} = \rho''_{\text{tot}} + 0.5(\rho'_{\text{tot}} - \rho''_{\text{tot}})$. From each block average profile, the vapor pressure as well as the densities ρ' and ρ'' and mole fractions x'_i and x''_i of the coexisting phases were determined as an average in the respective phase – excluding the direct vicinity of the interface.

Moreover, from the pressure and density profiles, equilibrium interfacial properties were computed, i.e. the surface tension, the relative adsorption, the enrichment, and the interfa-

cial thickness. The surface tension was obtained from the mechanical route

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (p_N - p_T) dz, \quad (4)$$

where p_N and p_T indicate the normal and tangential components of the pressure tensor^{103,104}, respectively.

The interface of the contact of two fluid phases can exhibit complex structures in mixtures^{33,83}. Therefore, different observables are usually used for describing the structure of the interface. Here, we use the relative adsorption, the enrichment, and the interfacial thickness. In this work, planar interfaces are considered. Hence, the structure can be characterized by the component density profiles $\rho_i(z)$ normal to the interface. The relative adsorption, the enrichment, and the interfacial thickness were computed from these profiles.

The relative adsorption of CO₂ in the interface with respect to H₂O $\Gamma_{\text{CO}_2}^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$ was computed according to the definition proposed by *Telo da Gama and Evans*^{41,105}

$$\Gamma_{\text{CO}_2}^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})} = -(\rho'_{\text{CO}_2} - \rho''_{\text{CO}_2}) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(z) - \rho'_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{\rho'_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - \rho''_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} - \frac{\rho_{\text{CO}_2}(z) - \rho'_{\text{CO}_2}}{\rho'_{\text{CO}_2} - \rho''_{\text{CO}_2}} \right] dz, \quad (5)$$

where ρ'_i and ρ''_i are the component densities of the coexisting bulk phases.

The non-monotonicity of the density profiles in the interface is usually quantified by the enrichment. We use the definition introduced by *Becker et al.*³² for computing the enrichment of CO₂ in the interface as

$$E_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{\max(\rho_{\text{CO}_2}(z))}{\max(\rho'_{\text{CO}_2}, \rho''_{\text{CO}_2})}, \quad (6)$$

where the nominator indicates the maximum of the CO₂ density profile in the interface and the denominator indicates the larger of the component densities in the two bulk phases.

Both, the relative adsorption $\Gamma_{\text{CO}_2}^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$ and the enrichment E_{CO_2} characterize the surface excess of carbon dioxide in the interface^{23,33}. Both are linked, but contain complementary information, cf. Refs.^{23,33,83}. The relative adsorption is an integral measure for the composition of the interface and the accumulation of a given component therein, cf. Eq. (5). Moreover, the relative adsorption is related to thermodynamic potentials via the Gibbs adsorption equation¹⁰⁶. The enrichment, on the other hand, is essentially an arbitrary (but convenient) property characterizing the relative peak height of a component density in the interface, cf. Eq. (6).

The position of the liquid slab and the positions of the interfaces are not fixed in the simulation box. They will in general slightly fluctuate during the simulation – also at equilibrium conditions. Three characteristic positions of the interface are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_{10} &= \rho'' + 0.1(\rho' - \rho'') , \\ \rho_{50} &= \rho'' + 0.5(\rho' - \rho'') , \\ \rho_{90} &= \rho'' + 0.9(\rho' - \rho'') ,\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

where $''$ indicates the vapor bulk phase and $'$ indicates the liquid bulk phase. The center of the interface $z_{50} = z(\rho_{50})$ was defined as the origin of a moving coordinate system following the fluctuations of the interface position in the simulation box. From the position values $z_{10} = z(\rho_{10})$ and $z_{90} = z(\rho_{90})$, the interfacial thickness L_{10}^{90} as proposed by *Lekner and Henderson*¹⁰⁷ was computed as

$$L_{10}^{90} = z(\rho_{90}) - z(\rho_{10}).\tag{8}$$

The statistical uncertainties of the sampled equilibrium interfacial properties (surface tension γ , relative adsorption $\Gamma_{\text{CO}_2}^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$, enrichment E_{CO_2} , and interfacial thickness L_{10}^{90}) as well as the bulk phase properties (vapor pressure p , saturated densities ρ' , ρ'' , and compositions \underline{x}' , \underline{x}'') were estimated as three times the standard deviation of the sampled block average values. From an extensive meta data study for a simple fluid, the systematical uncertainties (i.e. reproducibility of determining observables using different methods, simulation codes etc. by molecular simulation) has been estimated to be around $\pm 0.2\%$ and $\pm 1\%$ for the saturated liquid and vapor density, respectively, $\pm 1\%$ for the vapor pressure, and $\pm 4\%$ for the surface tension¹⁰⁸.

C. Non-Equilibrium MD simulations

For studying the mass transfer at vapor-liquid interfaces, the non-equilibrium simulation technique proposed in recent works of group^{57,60} was used. Fig. 1 schematically shows the working principle of the NEMD simulation method. The shape and size of the simulation box as well as equilibrated configurations were adapted from the EMD simulations (see above). Hence, the rectangular simulation box contains a mixture of the two components CO_2 and H_2O with a (CO_2 -rich) vapor phase in the middle and two (water-rich) liquid phases on

both sides. Again, periodic boundary conditions were used in all directions. After a short re-equilibration phase of the vapor-liquid equilibrium state (IniEq), a non-stationary molar flux of the low-boiling component CO_2 is induced by inserting CO_2 particles in the center of the vapor phase during the insertion phase (In). After the short insertion phase, the relaxation process (Relax) is monitored: CO_2 particles pass through the vapor phase and enter the liquid phase. The system thereby relaxes into a new vapor-liquid equilibrium state. During the relaxation process, spatially resolved responses for the component densities and fluxes are sampled. The system is thermostated throughout to maintain isothermal conditions. Thereby, the NEMD simulation method yields insights into the response of the system to a perturbation – in particular the interfacial mass transfer mechanisms – as it relaxes to a new vapor-liquid equilibrium state. To reduce the noise of the obtained observables and provide measures for the statistical uncertainty of the observables, sets of replicas of NEMD simulations^{57,109} are carried out. The insertion of the CO_2 particles is performed by a Monte Carlo algorithm^{110–112} in the so-called control volume (cf. Fig. 1). The Monte Carlo algorithm regulates the number of CO_2 particles based on a prescribed chemical potential of that component $\mu_{\text{CO}_2,\text{CV}}$ in the insertion phase (In). Particles are only inserted during the insertion phase (In). With the beginning of the particle insertion, a non-stationary molar flux j_{CO_2} from the center of the vapor phase towards the liquid interfaces sets in. The molar flux is positive on the right side of the control volume and negative on the left side of the control volume due to the symmetry of the simulation setup (cf. Fig. 1). Details on the simulation technique are given in Refs.^{57,60}.

In this work, the NEMD simulation technique was applied to study three related scenarios, which differ in their temperature, but have similar liquid phase composition at the beginning of the process. At least 20 replica simulations were carried out to study each state. In total, 96 NEMD simulations were conducted. Details are given in the Supplementary Material - Section I.

The number of inserted particles in a set of replicas varies due to the probabilistic nature of the Monte Carlo algorithm. The number for $\mu_{\text{CO}_2,\text{CV}}$ prescribed in the insertion phase was chosen such that the total number of inserted CO_2 particles was about 200 for a given simulation. The replicas were created from the final configuration of equilibrium simulations (as described above) by assigning randomized velocities to the molecules before the initial equilibration phase. The time step used for the NEMD simulations was $\delta\tau = 2$ fs. The

total time of the NEMD simulations was $\Delta\tau_{\text{Sim}} = 3.4$ ns. The length of the sampling of the first equilibrium state was $\Delta\tau_{\text{Eq1}} = 0.4$ ns, the length of the insertion interval was $\Delta\tau_{\text{In}} = 0.06$ ns, the length of the relaxation interval *Relax* was $\Delta\tau_{\text{Relax}} = 1.94$ ns, and the length of the sampling of the second equilibrium state was $\Delta\tau_{\text{Eq2}} = 1$ ns.

The simulation box was discretized in z -direction into 600 equally sized bins for determining density and flux profiles. The density profiles $\rho(\tau, z)$ were sampled as a function of the z -position and time τ every 10,000 simulation time steps. The molar local flux $j_{\text{CO}_2}(\tau, z)$ was determined from the local rate of change of the density $\partial\rho_{\text{CO}_2}/\partial\tau(\tau, z)$ and the molar balance for a bin n , which can be written as

$$\frac{\partial\rho_2}{\partial\tau}(\tau, n) = -\frac{j_2(\tau, n+1) - j_2(\tau, n)}{\Delta z_{\text{bin}}}, \quad (9)$$

where Δz_{bin} is the size of the bin and the index notation $n = 1 \dots N$ indicates the bins in z -direction. The flux at the left bin boundary is denoted with the index n and the flux at the right bin boundary with the index $n+1$. The $N+1$ local molar fluxes of the N bins were obtained from solving the N molar balances, i.e. Eq. (9), with a symmetry boundary condition (no net flux) at the periodic boundaries of the simulation box, cf. Fig. 1. The density and flux profile results obtained for a given time τ from all simulations of a set of replicas were averaged.

For characterizing the mass transfer processes in the vicinity of the interface, measurement volumes (MV) were defined: One in the vapor phase before the interface and one behind the interface in the liquid phase. MV_{vap} is located at a distance $\Delta z_{\text{off}} = 2.6433$ nm from the position z_{10} and MV_{liq} is located at a distance $\Delta z_{\text{off}} = 1.3216$ nm from the position z_{90} . Different values were chosen for MV_{vap} and MV_{liq} since the total density profile $\rho(z)$ is less steep on the vapor side of the interface compared to the liquid side. The width of each MV is $\Delta z_{\text{MV}} = 0.52$ nm. Details of the sampling method can be found in Refs.^{57,60}.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Equilibrium properties

Fig. 2 shows the results for the Henry's law constants of CO_2 in water obtained using the adjusted binary interaction parameter ξ . Results from the MD model are compared to experimental data in the entire temperature range where experimental data are available.

In the temperature range that was used for the model adjustment, the agreement of the MD results and the experimental data is very good. At higher temperatures, the MD results qualitatively describe the experimental data well, but slightly overestimate them. Yet, in that temperature range, also the experimental data reported by different groups scatter significantly.

Fig. 3 shows isothermal phase diagrams of the binary mixture $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$ at $T = 291.65 \text{ K}$, 372.08 K , and 452.97 K . The MD results from the direct VLE simulations are compared to PCP-SAFT equation of state results. At the studied temperatures, no experimental phase equilibrium data is available. The MD simulation results that were obtained with the state-independent binary interaction parameter ξ are in good agreement with the EOS results in the entire composition range for all three studied temperatures.

The binary mixture $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$ is a type III mixture in the classification scheme of *van Konynenburg and Scott*¹⁵. Hence, the binary mixture is highly non-ideal. This is a consequence of the molecular interactions in the mixture that are strongly different for the two components, i.e. water is a highly polar molecule with strong H-bonding, whereas CO_2 is a molecule with dominating dispersive interactions and a quadrupole moment. As a result, CO_2 is only poorly soluble in water. At some conditions (not considered here), the mixture exhibits a liquid-liquid and vapor-liquid-liquid equilibrium^{12,13}. The presence of a liquid-liquid and vapor-liquid-liquid equilibrium in a given system also has important consequences vapor-liquid interfacial properties and favors strong enrichment^{113,114}.

The vapor-liquid equilibrium interfacial properties obtained from the direct VLE MD simulations are depicted in Fig. 4, where results are shown for the surface tension, the relative adsorption, and the enrichment of CO_2 at the interface as a function of the liquid phase concentration x'_{CO_2} . The results for the interfacial thickness are presented in the Supplementary Material - Section II. Fig. 5 shows the corresponding equilibrium density profiles for all studied state points.

Water is known to have a particularly high surface tension. The surface tension obtained from the TIP4P/2005 force field describes the surface tension of water reasonably well^{115,116}. At the studied conditions, no experimental mixture surface tension data is available. We compared our MD results for the mixture surface tension with the DGT model from Ref.¹³ (which describes experimental surface tension data well) and found good agreement. From the MD results obtained in this work, cf. Fig. 4, it can be seen that the temperature depen-

dency and composition dependency of the surface tension is as expected, i.e. it decreases with increasing temperature and increasing liquid phase mole fraction of the low-boiling component.

Due to the strong non-ideality of the mixture behavior, also a large surface excess is obtained. The large surface excess manifests as large relative adsorption and large enrichment of CO_2 in the interface, cf. Fig. 3-middle and bottom. This is in agreement with results reported in the literature^{12,13,33}. In fact, the system $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$ is the system with the largest enrichment that has so far been observed³³. For many other systems, the enrichment of low-boiling components i is usually only up to about $E_i \approx 3$ ^{33-35,117,118}. For the binary mixture $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$, an exceptionally high enrichment of up to $E_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 8$ is obtained in the studied temperature and composition range. The temperature and composition dependency of the enrichment is in line with what has been observed for most other mixtures in the literature³³, i.e. it decreases with increasing temperature and increasing liquid phase mole fraction of the low-boiling component, cf. Fig. 4-bottom. To the best of our knowledge, the enrichment in molecular systems has not yet been confirmed by laboratory experiments. For the relative adsorption, on the other hand, predictions from molecular simulations were found many times to be in good agreement with experimental data^{32,37,83}. Yet, for the system $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$, no experimental adsorption data is available for the temperatures studied here. Qualitatively, the results for $\Gamma_{\text{CO}_2}^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}(T, x'_{\text{CO}_2})$ (cf. Fig. 4-middle) are as expected, i.e. $\Gamma_{\text{CO}_2}^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$ increases with decreasing temperature and increasing liquid phase mole fraction of the low-boiling component.

The equilibrium density profiles shown in Fig. 5 are in line with the findings discussed above. The low CO_2 solubility in the liquid phase can be seen from the large differences in the CO_2 densities in the liquid and the vapor bulk phase. For the interfacial region, it can be seen from Fig. 5 that the absolute peak height and peak width increases with increasing x'_{CO_2} (which corresponds to an increase in pressure, cf. Fig. 3) and with decreasing T . This is reflected in the relative adsorption $\Gamma_{\text{CO}_2}^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$ (cf. Fig. 4-middle). Hence, the interface has a strongly increasing capacity to host CO_2 particles with increasing x'_{CO_2} and with decreasing T at phase equilibrium conditions.

B. Non-Equilibrium properties

Starting from the equilibrium mixture states (cf. green symbols in Fig. 3 and green lines in Fig. 5), non-equilibrium simulations were carried as described in Section II C, in which CO₂ particles were inserted in the vapor phase and the mass transfer resulting from this perturbation was monitored. The results presented in the main body are averages of all replicas from a given set of replicas. In the Supplementary Material - Section III, a discussion of the scattering of the results from the individual simulations within a replica set is given. Fig. 6 shows the results for the CO₂ density and mass flux in the two measurement volumes (cf. scheme in Fig. 1) as a function of the simulation time. Fig. 6 (a) and (c) show the results for the vapor phase measurement volume; Fig. 6 (b) and (d) those for the liquid phase measurement volume. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the density and flux profiles as a function of the spatial coordinate at selected simulation times.

Quickly after the end of the insertion phase *In*, CO₂ particles arrive in the vapor phase measurement volume MV_{vap} close to the interface resulting in an increase of the density ρ''_{CO_2} , cf. Fig. 6 (a). At the beginning of the relaxation phase *Relax*, oscillations are observed in the sampled $\rho''_{\text{CO}_2}(\tau)$ signal. These oscillations quickly decay until about $\tau = 0.9$ ns. The oscillations are a result of CO₂ particles that are repelled from the interface back into the vapor bulk phase. This is supported by the results for the sampled mass flux j_{CO_2} in the vapor phase measurement volume MV_{vap} , which show a negative net flux (outside the scattering of the results) for short periods of time. The short-lived damped oscillation are explained as follows: When the repelled CO₂ particles reach the symmetry plane in the center of the simulation box again, they can collide with the symmetric mass flux that was repelled from the other interface (cf. symmetry in Fig. 1). Hence, while the repelling of the particles is a physical phenomenon that is related to the mass transfer, the oscillations are related to the special choice of the simulation set-up and can be considered an artifact. Such a repelling of particles from the interface has also been observed in mass transfer simulations of a highly non-ideal (also type III) Lennard-Jones mixture⁵⁷. It was assumed in Ref.⁵⁷ that this repelling of particles from the interface was related to a high surface tension and enrichment. This is supported by the results from the this work, as the system studied here has a particularly high surface tension and enrichment.

After the relaxation process, a new equilibrium state *Eq2* is established regarding both,

the bulk and the interfacial properties. Yet, no significant changes are observed for the liquid phase, cf. Fig. 6 (b). This is a consequence of: 1) the gas solubility of CO₂ in the liquid phase being very low; 2) the number of inserted particles was small to keep the effect of the perturbation on the system moderate; 3) a substantial part of the inserted CO₂ particles is absorbed by the interface; and 4) the signal-to-noise ratio for the sampled liquid phase mole fraction x'_{CO_2} and flux in the liquid phase j_{CO_2} is fairly low – despite the fact that at least 20 replica simulations were carried out and averaged. As a result, the net flux of CO₂ into the liquid phase is so small that it cannot be detected, cf. Fig. 6 (b) and (d). Therefore, no significant amount of CO₂ particles passes the interface and enters the liquid bulk phase.

The results for the different properties sampled in the measurement volumes, cf. Fig. 6, are qualitatively similar for the different temperatures albeit at different levels of the densities. Only the amplitude of the damped oscillations appears to slightly increase with decreasing temperature. This supports the hypothesis that the enrichment and the surface tension are important for the repelling of the particles from the interface, since these two properties also increase with decreasing temperature, cf. Fig. 4.

Figs. 7 and 8 show the time evolution of the density profiles (left) and flux profiles (right) in the vicinity of the interfacial region. The profiles are shown in a region that extends about 6 nm into the vapor and 2 nm into the liquid phase. The spatial coordinate normal to the interface is denoted as $z - z_{50}$, where z_{50} indicates the middle of the interfacial region. The interface spans the region from approximately $-2 \text{ nm} < (z - z_{50}) < 2 \text{ nm}$, cf. Fig. 7. Since the depicted profiles were obtained from averaging over x and y , this thickness comprises the roughness of the interface. The density and flux profiles provide detailed insights into the mass transport processes at the interface. Two main mechanisms are observed: 1) The repelling of particles at the interface back into the vapor phase and a damped oscillatory repetition of that mechanism; 2) a momentary single-event drain of the interface. Both mechanisms are discussed separately in the following; Fig. 7 focuses on 2), while Fig. 8 focuses on 1). The mechanism 1) was already observed in the time evolution of the density in the measurement volumes, cf. Fig. 6. Yet, the mechanism 2) starts before the mechanism 1) in the non-stationary process. Fig. 7 shows the profiles for the time interval $\tau = [0.4...0.52] \text{ ns}$ that covers the end of the insertion phase and the beginning of the relaxation phase; Fig. 8 shows the results for the subsequent part of the relaxation phase $\tau = [0.56...1.4] \text{ ns}$ until the second equilibrium state *Eq2* is reached. For clarity, results are

only shown for selected block averages (more results are presented in the Supplementary Material - Section III).

Since all considered state points start from an equilibrium mixture state (cf. green symbols in Fig. 3 and green lines in Fig. 5), a significant enrichment and adsorption of CO₂ at the interface is observed already at the beginning of the insertion phase *In*, cf. Fig. 7 (a), (c), and (e). While the time evolution of the density profiles (Figs. 7 (a), (c), (e) and Figs. 8 (a), (c), (e)) is overall straightforward to comprehend, the flux profiles (Figs. 7 (b), (d), (f) and Figs. 8 (b), (d), (f)) are more complex and deserve a brief general discussion: Immediately after the start of the insertion, i.e. at $\tau \approx 0.4$ ns, CO₂ particles have not arrived in the vicinity of the interface and $j_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 0$, accordingly. Still, some fluctuations for j_{CO_2} are observed at that time that are due to (i) fluctuations due to the thermal motion without a net flux being present; (ii) differences in the thermal motion in the individual replica simulations within a set of replicas. In the equilibrium states (*Eq1* and *Eq2*), e.g. the profiles at $\tau \approx 0.4$ ns (cf. Figs. 7 (a)), the mean fluxes obtained from a replica set fluctuate at around $\approx 10,000$ mol m⁻²s⁻¹ in the vapor bulk phase and with about ≈ 500 mol m⁻²s⁻¹ in the liquid bulk phase. This reflects the differences in the self-diffusion coefficients in the two phases, i.e. the dynamic equilibrium properties.

Focusing on the interface region at the beginning of the relaxation process (cf. Fig. 7), the momentary drain mechanism 2) can be observed. This drainage occurs approximately at the center of the interface. This is an unexpected effect occurring at the beginning of the relaxation process. In Fig. 7, results for all three studied state points are shown (top to bottom). Since the mechanism 2) is overall similar for the three studied temperatures, we focus in the discussion first on the results for $T = 291.65$ K. At about $\tau \approx 0.48$ ns, the interface widens, i.e. the enrichment peak of the low-boiling component CO₂ decreases and becomes broader, cf. Fig. 7 (e). This is also reflected by the mass flux profile, cf. Fig. 7 (f). Additionally, the high-boiling component density profile $\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ widens. At about $\tau \approx 0.48$ ns, a positive mass flux j_{CO_2} is observed on the liquid side of the interface, which pushes some CO₂ particles into the liquid phase (cf. Fig. 7 (f)). On the vapor side of the interface, on the other hand, CO₂ particles are pushed out of the interface into the vapor phase. Quickly afterwards (at about $\tau \approx 0.52$ ns), the mass fluxes at the interface are reversed, i.e. CO₂ particles move from the liquid side of the interface back into the interface (negative j_{CO_2} at $(z - z_{50}) > 0$) as well as from the vapor side of the interface back into the interface (positive

j_{CO_2} at $(z - z_{50}) < 0$). The position of zero flux during this mechanism is approximately located at the peak position of the CO_2 density (comparing Fig. 7 (e) and (f)). Hence, CO_2 is momentarily depleted from the interface and then re-accumulates at the interface. Thereby, the interface momentarily broadens. The starting point is the *Eq1* equilibrium state; the ending state is the *Eq2* state. The CO_2 particle drain starts before the net flux of particles arrives at the interface, which is at approximately $\tau \approx 0.52$ ns, cf. Fig. 7 (f). The pressure, on the other side, reaches the corresponding *Eq2* value significantly faster throughout the simulation box in the mass transfer simulations^{57,60} – see also Supplementary Material - Section III. Therefore, we hypothesize that, at the interface, the pressure jump caused by the perturbation affects the interfacial properties before the actual mass flux arrives at the interface, i.e. the enrichment peak decreases and the interfacial thickness increases. This is in accordance with the pressure dependency of the equilibrium properties, cf. Figs. 3 and 4. The drain mechanism observed in the simulations might also be related to the surface roughness and xy -averaging used for the sampling of the profiles.

This momentary drain mechanism is most prominent at low temperatures (cf. Fig. 7 (e), (f)), but present to a significant extent at all studied temperatures (cf. Fig. 7 (a)-(d)). At the highest studied temperature, the vapor side depletion of the interface is not strong enough to yield a zero flux at the center of the interface at $\tau \approx 0.48$ ns. The liquid side drain is more prominent than on the vapor side, which is probably due to the superposition of the net mass flux of arriving CO_2 particles at the interface.

The density profiles provide further detailed insights into the oscillatory fluxes observed in the vapor phase, i.e. mechanism 1). A significant net flux of CO_2 particles in the vapor phase towards the interface is observed in Fig. 7 (b), (d), (f) at about $\tau = [0.48...0.52]$ ns (depending on the temperature). Yet, a zero flux j_{CO_2} is maintained in the liquid bulk phase in all cases (throughout the relaxation process). Hence, no (significant number of) particles pass the interface and enter the liquid bulk phase. On the contrary, a significant amount of particles is repelled from the interface and a negative flux j_{CO_2} is at times observed in the vapor phase, cf. Fig. 8 (b), (d), (f). Due to the simulation box geometry, this repelled flux returns eventually to the interface, but decays as the second equilibrium state *Eq2* is established. This yields a damped oscillatory behavior. The oscillatory flux behavior can be seen in the dark blue profiles in Fig. 8 (b), (d), and (f) that oscillate until about $\tau \approx 0.8$ ns. The maximum amplitude of the flux oscillations is approximately $20,000 \text{ mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. This

oscillatory behavior is in line with the observables monitored in the vapor phase measurement volumes MV_{vap} , cf. Fig. 6. At about $\tau > 0.9$ ns, the flux oscillations decayed and the flux j_{CO_2} is mostly slightly positive on the vapor side of the interfacial region and in the vapor bulk phase, cf. e.g. Fig. 8 (f). In that simulation phase, no significant flux is observed anymore on the liquid side of the interfacial region, i.e. mechanism 2) has practically ended. At about $\tau \approx 1.1$ ns, only the equilibrium flux fluctuations remain – mostly in the vapor phase.

More detailed insights can be obtained regarding the particle repelling from the interface. The position of the particle repelling can be identified from the location, where the oscillatory fluxes (dark blue profiles in Fig. 7 (b), (d), (f)) become zero, which is at the left side edge of the interfacial region. This point moves towards the vapor side comparing the results from the different temperatures, i.e. comparing Fig. 7 (b) to (d) to (f). This is in line with the interfacial thickness of the *Eq1* state being increasing for the three studied state points, cf. Fig. 7 (a), (c), (e) and the Supplementary Material.

Since, practically no CO_2 particles enter the liquid phase, the inserted CO_2 molecules result in an increase of the vapor phase density and yields an increase of the adsorption of CO_2 in the interface. This is also reflected by the density profiles, cf. Fig. 8 (a), (c), and (e). The absolute height of the enrichment peak increases and the interfacial thickness decreases until they finally reach their equilibrium *Eq2* values. The (absolute) peak height in the *Eq2* state is higher than that of the *Eq1* state, which reflects a higher relative adsorption and is in accordance with the equilibrium interfacial properties, cf. Fig. 4.

The two mechanisms 1) and 2) are probably not directly related. They can be spatially located to different parts of the interface and in parts different times of the relaxation process. While the (oscillatory) repelling of particles occurs on the vapor side edge of the interface (repelled particles do not significantly enter the interfacial region), the momentary drain occurs in the entire interface.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A molecular dynamics simulation study of equilibrium and non-equilibrium vapor-liquid interfacial properties of the binary system water + carbon dioxide was carried out. This provides insights in the relation of the structure of the interface and mass transfer mecha-

nisms.

NEMD simulations of mass transfer at vapor-liquid interfaces are challenging, e.g. the perturbation of the system can quickly yield an unwanted condensation of small droplets in the vapor phase and the fluctuating position of the interface poses significant challenges for the sampling. Moreover, finding an appropriate magnitude of the perturbation, i.e. the amount and rate of inserted particles, is a tedious task such that a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio is obtained on one hand, and, on the other hand, the simulation proceeds in a stable way. Despite these (and other) challenges, the non-stationary simulation method proposed in an earlier work of our group⁵⁷ was found to be applicable to study the mass transfer in the strongly interacting real substance binary system $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$ and has yielded significant and detailed insights into the mass transfer processes on the atomistic level. This work also demonstrates that this simulation method can be applied not only to simple fluid systems, but also to complex real substance systems.

In comparison to simple fluid mixtures, the system $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$ shows special features – for both equilibrium and non-equilibrium properties. At the vapor-liquid interface of the mixture $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$, the low-boiling component CO_2 has a very high enrichment, which also yields a large adsorption of CO_2 at the interface. Moreover, the surface tension of the system is very high (due to the water pure component properties). The interfacial properties interact with the mass transfer in a peculiar way such that a significant amount of the inserted CO_2 particles is repelled from the interface initially and a negative net flux back into the vapor phase is meanwhile obtained.

Moreover, the interesting effect of 'momentary drainage' of the interface is observed: The interfacial thickness and enrichment peak broadens and the heights of the enrichment peak decreases at the very beginning of the process, which is most likely due to the pressure increase caused by the perturbation. This goes in hand with a flux of CO_2 particles from the center of the interface to the edges of the interface. After this initial broadening of the interface and decrease of the enrichment peak, the drainage is reversed and the new equilibrium state is established. For future work, it would be interesting to investigate the relation of the observed momentary drainage and the fluid interface roughness.

The vapor-liquid interface of the system $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$ acts as a significant hindrance for mass transfer entering the liquid phase: Firstly, a significant net repelling of CO_2 molecules from the interface is observed; Secondly, the interface itself adsorbs a significant amount of

CO₂ molecules.

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FIG. 1: Scheme of the NEMD simulation setup. Light blue indicates vapor phase; dark blue indicates liquid phase. During the insertion phase, CO_2 particles are inserted into the control volume (gray area). For a short time after which the insertion ends, the inserted particles propagate through the vapor phase and enter the interface. The yellow dashed areas indicate sampling volumes in which properties of the bulk vapor phase and the bulk liquid phase near the vapor-liquid interface were measured.

FIG. 2: Henry's law constant of carbon dioxide in water as a function of the temperature. Crosses indicate experimental data from the Dortmund database (DDB)⁹⁰; Blue circles indicate MD simulation results of the adjusted mixture model.

FIG. 3: Phase diagrams of the system water + carbon dioxide at the three studied temperatures: $T = 452.97$ K (top), $T = 372.08$ K (middle), and $T = 291.65$ K (bottom).

Lines indicate PCP-SAFT EOS¹³ results; symbols indicate MD simulation phase equilibrium results: Triangles for the vapor phase and circles for the liquid phase. Green symbols represent the phases used as starting point in the NEMD simulations.

FIG. 4: Equilibrium interfacial properties of the system water + carbon dioxide as a function of the liquid phase mole fraction for the three investigated temperatures. Results from MD simulations. Top: surface tension; middle: relative adsorption of CO₂; bottom: enrichment of CO₂. Green symbols indicate the state points used as starting point in the NEMD simulations.

FIG. 5: Equilibrium density profiles of the system water + carbon dioxide at the three studied temperatures: $T = 452.97$ K (top), $T = 372.08$ K (middle), and $T = 291.65$ K (bottom). Results for different bulk liquid phase mole fraction x'_{CO_2} (color coded). Dashed lines indicate H_2O ; solid lines indicate CO_2 . Green lines indicate the results that were used as starting point in the NEMD simulations.

FIG. 6: Non-equilibrium simulation results for densities and fluxes sampled in the measurement volumes MV_{vap} and MV_{liq} in the vapor and liquid phase, respectively, as a function of the time τ . Results shown for the three studied temperatures (color coded). Top: Density CO₂, bottom: Flux of CO₂. The different intervals of the simulation are indicated on the time axis.

FIG. 7: Results from non-equilibrium mass transfer simulations in the system water + CO₂: density and flux profiles as a function of the z -coordinate in the vicinity of the interface at the beginning of the process ($\tau = [0.4..0.52]$ ns). Results are shown in (a)-(b) for $T = 452.97$ K, (c)-(d) for $T = 372.08$ K, and (e)-(f) for $T = 291.65$ K. The interface is located at $z - z_{50} = 0$. The simulation time is indicated by color and the profiles are displayed at intervals of $\Delta\tau = 0.04$ ns. For the density profiles, full lines indicate CO₂ and dotted lines H₂O.

FIG. 8: Results from non-equilibrium mass transfer simulations in the system water + CO₂: density and flux profiles as a function of the z -coordinate in the vicinity of the interface at the end of the process ($\tau = [0.56...1.4]$ ns). Results are shown in (a)-(b) for $T = 452.97$ K, (c)-(d) for $T = 372.08$ K, and (e)-(f) for $T = 291.65$ K. The interface is located at $z - z_{50} = 0$. The simulation time is indicated by color and the profiles are displayed at intervals of $\Delta\tau = 0.04$ ns. For the density profiles, full lines indicate CO₂ and dotted lines H₂O.

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